

Designing RF-Powered Battery-Less Electronic Shelf Labels With COTS Components

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Abstract—This paper presents a preliminary study exploring the feasibility of designing batteryless electronic shelf labels (ESLs) powered by radio frequency wireless power transfer using commercial off-the-shelf components. The proposed ESL design is validated through a dedicated testbed and involves a detailed analysis of design choices, including energy consumption, energy conversion, and storage solutions. A leaded aluminium electrolytic capacitor is selected as the primary energy storage element, balancing cost and performance while maintaining compactness. Experimental evaluations demonstrate that an ESL can update its display within 4 to 120 minutes, depending on input power and RF frequency, with harvester efficiencies reaching up to 30%. Challenges such as low harvester efficiency, extended update times, and hardware constraints are identified, highlighting opportunities for future optimizations. This work provides valuable insights into system design considerations for RF-powered ESLs and establishes a foundation for further research in energy-neutral Internet of Things applications.

Index Terms—electronic shelf label, RF-based wireless power transfer, energy-neutral device

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent studies and dedicated projects have focused on energy-neutral devices (ENDs) [1–3], making it a key topic in ongoing 6G research. One specific use case is electronic shelf labels (ESLs), which have low energy and reliability requirements and are produced in large quantities. Currently, different market players implement their own power and communication solutions for these ESLs, which are proprietary. This paper investigates a potential implementation while identifying improvements and trade-offs through experiments focused on energy consumption, conversion, and storage. It offers a comprehensive overview of key considerations and design guidelines for developing such devices.

Device Classes. This work focuses on Class 2 devices, as defined in [4, Sec. 3.1], to address the specific challenges of ESLs. Reindeer [4] categorized devices into five classes based on energy supply and communication capabilities. Class 1 devices, relying solely on radio frequency (RF) energy through wireless power transfer (WPT) and backscatter communication, and are unsuitable due to the buffering required for energy-intensive screen updates. Conversely, Class 3 devices, commonly used in commercial ESLs, rely on batteries or wireless charging, which this study aims to avoid. Class 2 devices, being energy-neutral and battery-free, are ideal for updating electronic paper displays (EPDs) in low-power scenarios.

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Fig. 1: ESL design with the AEM40940 harvester and references to the sections where each component is elaborated.

Literature. ESLs can be powered via an internal battery or externally via ambient or RF-based techniques. For example, [5, 6] present battery-powered ESL designs with wireless communication system, achieving an autonomy of approximately 3 year. Research focusing on energy harvesters using solar power and 1 F electrostatic double-layer capacitors (EDLC) buffer can be found in [7]. However, this work focuses on RF-based WPT. Various RF WPT techniques have been proposed to supply energy to low-power batteryless devices, as demonstrated in [8, 9]. A recent study in [10] on RF-powered ESL has primarily focused on voltage conversion techniques and efficiency optimization, with less emphasis on storage and peripheral device power consumption. Several commercial solutions claim advancements in RF-powered ESL technology [11, 12]. The white paper in [11], introduces batteryless EPD solutions that requires a user to move through the store with a reader to update the ESLs, or alternatively, a robotic system could be deployed to automate this process. The authors claim a coverage range of 24 m. However, the feasibility of this claim requires further evaluation, as at that distance the path loss exceeds 60 dB. WPT transmission at 30 dBm (as advertised) yields then a received power of only -30 dBm, which falls below the sensitivity of the used harvester (-17 dBm) [13] and other conventional energy harvesters (-20 dBm) [14]. Consequently, *achieving reliable energy transfer under these conditions remains highly challenging. This highlights the need for validated designs that are accessible and reproducible.*

Contributions. Our main contributions include the development of a novel RF-powered ESL, emphasizing the integration of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components to achieve a minimalistic and resource-efficient architecture. The design prioritizes the use of a low-cost and compact buffer capacitor. Furthermore, we experimentally validated and evaluated the system. This includes a detailed analysis of the ESL’s response time based on the energy consumption of the EPD, COTS

harvester, and storage buffer. This investigation provides new insights into system performance and architectural design of RF-powered ESLs, as was lacking in prior research.

Outline. The remainder of the paper is as follows. In Section II, we define the system requirements and present the proposed ESL architecture, detailing the selected microcontroller, harvester, and energy storage technologies based on the identified requirements and design constraints. Section III focuses on the experimental validation and evaluation of the ESL, including analyses of buffer charge time, efficiency, optimal RF frequency, and optimal buffer capacity. In Section IV, we provide an overview of techniques to enhance the efficiency of WPT. Finally, the paper concludes with a summary of findings and a discussion of potential future work in Section V.

II. ESL REQUIREMENTS AND ARCHITECTURE

This section outlines the system requirements for an RF-powered ESL capable of performing screen updates. Based on these requirements, the study evaluates an ESL built with COTS components, selecting a suitable EPD and microcontroller to control the screen. Additionally, the energy needed for an EPD update is measured, and the component design is analyzed considering constraints like buffer size, voltage ranges of the harvester, and booster converter. The final design is illustrated in Fig. 1.

A. System Requirements and Design Constraints

The system is designed to implement a functional Class 2 END that operates efficiently under stringent constraints. The requirements (R) and assumptions (A) guiding the design are as follows:

- R1** Minimize the energy buffer capacity to a single operation per full charge, i.e., an EPD update.
- R2** Power the device exclusively with an external RF energy source.
- R3** Utilize COTS components to ensure cost-effectiveness and accessibility.
- R4** Optimize, i.e., minimize, the charge time to maximize system responsiveness.
- R5** Maximize receiver sensitivity, to charge at low RF input powers.
- R6** Minimize the energy consumption of peripheral hardware.
- R7** Minimize the physical size of the ESL.
- A1** Impact of communication is not considered.

B. RF Frequency Band Selection

To address practical restrictions, a brief analysis is conducted to identify the most suitable frequency bands for RF-based WPT of ESLs (R1). Sub-1 GHz frequencies are preferred due to their lower attenuation compared to higher frequencies and the regulatory allowance for higher transmission powers in these bands. For instance, in Europe, a maximum transmit power of 4 W (915–921 MHz) and 2 W (865–868 MHz) is allowed [15].¹

¹Consult the regulations for more details on the specific bands and channel usage.

C. System Hardware Design

Although it would be possible to directly charge the microcontroller unit (MCU) and EPD from the harvester, a storage element of buffer is added. This improves the sensitivity of the harvester, i.e., it lowers the minimum required RF power on which the device can operate (R5). To optimally use the energy buffer, the system needs to cope with a wide voltage range, when the buffer is being discharged. By doing so, the required capacity of the buffer can be reduced, minimizing both the initial charge time (R4) and the required capacitance (R1). It hence becomes essential to expand the dynamic range of the input voltage of the buffer and provide a stable output voltage to the MCU and EPD.

D. ePaper display and Microcontroller

In this study, an Adafruit evaluation board featuring a 2.13-inch monochrome eInk/ePaper display² was selected. To refresh and communicate with the EPD, an ultra-low-power Arm Cortex-M0+ microcontroller is selected. The selected board operates at 3.3 V, eliminating the need for level shifters between the display and MCU. One update takes 5.2 s and requires 75 mJ as measured with the Oti Arc.

E. Energy Storage Element and Boost Converter

The capacitance of a capacitor is determined by the two voltage thresholds that define the operating range for updating the ESL. The maximum charging voltage, determined by the harvester, is referred to as the cut-off voltage $V_{\text{cutt-off}}$. Additionally, the minimum input voltage of the boost converter $V_{\text{boost, min}}$ determines the lowest usable voltage to which the capacitor can be discharged while still achieving the desired output voltage of 3.3 V. Consequently, the capacitance can be calculated using:

$$C_B = \frac{2E_{\text{update}}}{V_{\text{cutt-off}}^2 - V_{\text{boost, min}}^2}. \quad (1)$$

F. RF Harvester – Charging and Triggering Update

The selected COTS harvester achieves efficiency levels of up to 30 percent, including tuning and power management unit (PMU) efficiency [16]. The PMU, inside the harvester, (R3) serves two primary functions in our design: charging the storage element (capacitor) and enabling the boost converter to wake up the microcontroller (Fig. 1).

The harvester is designed to accommodate various battery and capacitor technologies, with its configuration determining the voltage range for charging. This range is constrained by the overvoltage protection threshold, V_{ovch} . The harvester includes two Low-dropout voltage regulators (LDOs), a low-voltage glsldo and a high-voltage LDO, to power peripherals using the attached storage element. Seven configurable settings define the overvoltage protection voltage, the activation and deactivation thresholds for the LDOs, and the output voltages provided by both LDOs. The choice of configuration depends on the storage element's technology.

²Adafruit 2.13" eInk Display Breakouts and FeatherWings.

To wake up the microcontroller when the capacitor is sufficiently charged (V_{chrdy}), the low-voltage LDO activates the boost converter, which, in turn, powers the microcontroller. By utilizing the low-voltage LDO to enable the boost converter, the need for additional hardware and energy consumption is significantly reduced (R6). The ORing circuit, connected to one of the microcontroller’s General-Purpose Input/Outputs (GPIOs), overrides the low-voltage LDO output ($LVOUT$) when the capacitor voltage falls below V_{ovdis} . Without this mechanism, the capacitor’s usable voltage range would be limited to between 2.8 V (V_{ovdis}) and 3.1 V (V_{chrdy}), utilizing only 18.4 % of its energy. By leveraging the full voltage range, the required capacitor capacity is significantly reduced (R1, R4).

Using Eq. (1) and taking into account the minimum voltage of the boost converter (0.9 V), a minimum capacitor size of 17 mF is calculated, allowing 91.6 % of the capacitor’s energy to be utilized. To account for additional losses and to follow the E12-series, a 22 mF capacitor is used in this design.

G. Capacitor Technology

Film, ceramic, tantalum, and polymer capacitors typically do not provide capacitance values in the millifarad range, are severely limited, or are prohibitively expensive. This in contrast to EDLCs and aluminum electrolytic capacitors (AECs). While AECs are available with capacitance values up to several tens of millifarads, their low energy density can lead to undesired large dimensions (R7). EDLCs, with their higher energy density, present a promising alternative. Table I summarizes three options for this ESL application.

TABLE I: Energy storage proposals considered during the selection process. (lower is better)

Technology	(1) EDLC	(2) EDLC	(3) AEC
Type	FYD0H223ZF	FYH0H105ZF	ECA-0JM223
Capacitance	22 mF	1 F	22 mF
Volume	1.2 cm ³	7.0 cm ³	9.0 cm ³
Boost required	Yes	No	Yes
ESR	200 Ω	20 Ω	0.05 Ω
Charge time (Fig. 3)	same	longer	same
Cost	≈ € 3	≈ € 6	≈ € 1.5
Usable	No (ESR)	Yes	Yes

The second option is similar to the first, with the significant difference that its capacitance is 45 times higher. This is required due to the high equivalent series resistance (ESR), yielding high internal losses. This issue is no longer a concern, when increasing the capacity (Option 2). Additionally, a boost converter would not be required, as 885 mJ is available within the voltage range of 2.8–3.1 V. However, the initial charging time would become undesirably long, particularly when the buffer capacitor is fully discharged. Despite the slightly larger dimensions, the third option, proves to be the most suitable storage technology. Its low ESR ensures that internal losses are negligible. Additionally, its cost is generally lower than that of EDLCs. With the proposed architecture from Fig. 1,

the ESL can perform an update within 4–120 min depending on the input power (Fig. 3).

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION AND VALIDATION

The implemented ESL, as presented in Fig. 2, is evaluated by charging the selected 22 mF capacitor (Section II-G) using an RF generator (SMC100A) at 868 and 920 MHz. The evaluation includes measuring the charge time (Section III-A) and charge efficiency (Section III-B) under different input powers and RF bands.

Fig. 2: Prototype demonstration of the proposed ESL architecture. The black box in the upper right corner includes two connectors, allowing real-time voltage monitoring of the capacitor.

A. Charge Time of the Buffer Capacitor

Figure 3 illustrates the measured charging time of a 22 mF AEC up to a voltage of 3.1 V. The harvester exhibits slightly improved performance at a frequency of 868 MHz. Specifically, for lower input voltage levels, the charging time at 868 MHz is reduced by several minutes compared to 920 MHz, given the same input power level. The reason is that harvester itself is optimally tuned for 868 MHz.

Fig. 3: Measured time to charge the buffer capacitor of 22 mF to 3.1 V with the AEM40940 harvester.

B. Harvester Charge Efficiency

As shown in Fig. 3, charging logically occurs much faster at higher input power levels. However, this is not necessarily the most energy-efficient. The required input RF energy at the harvester is significantly higher at higher RF input power levels, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Hence, the charge efficiency, i.e., the ratio of required input energy to the nominal energy of the buffer, decreases with input RF power. The efficiency naturally takes into account the tuning losses, the harvester AC/DC conversion and the PMU losses to charge the capacitor.

Fig. 4: Measured efficiency related to the RF input energy and the stored energy in the buffer.

The charging efficiency depends, among others, on the initial voltage over the capacitor. In Fig. 5, the measured charge efficiency is depicted with respect to this initial capacitor voltage. As can be observed, the higher the initial voltage, the higher the charge efficiency. Only considering this, a higher capacity would be desirable as it would be operating at a higher voltage and would consequently require a lower voltage range. For example, a 1 F (option 2 in Table I) EDLC capacitor, would have sufficient energy in the voltage range 3.0–3.1 V. Furthermore, this would mean that no boost converter would be necessary. The downside of the higher capacity is the increased initial charge time, a higher ESR ($\times 400$), increased size (depending on the technology) and cost ($\times 4$).

IV. TECHNIQUES TO DELIVER ENERGY TO ESLs

The transmit side is also important to consider, although this is not the focus of this paper, and it does not impact the findings and conclusions made here. Various RF-based strategies and technologies can be utilized to deliver sufficient power to the ESL. Power transfer can be achieved using either a single antenna or multiple antennas, with the latter offering, among others, higher received power and improved transfer efficiency compared to a single-antenna setup [9].

Recent studies have investigated leveraging environmental information to coherently combine RF signals at the ESLs, relying solely on geometric details of the environment, ESL, and antenna positions [17, 18]. Beyond geometry-based methods, reciprocity-based approaches use an uplink pilot to learn

Fig. 5: Measured harvester efficiency at 868 MHz as a function of the capacitor voltage for input power levels of -5 dBm and 10 dBm.

the downlink channel from the uplink channel, as discussed in [18]. However, both approaches have limitations: geometry-based methods require accurate positional information, and reciprocity-based techniques depend on sufficient initial on-board energy to transmit the pilot signal. To address these initial access challenges, several alternative techniques have been proposed in the literature, such as random-phase sweeping and high-peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) transmission [17, 19–21].

The multi-antenna coherent WPT system is demonstrated using our testbed, receiving 0 dBm at the ESL. [22] This enables the screen to update every 25 min.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This preliminary study demonstrates the feasibility of a batteryless ESL system powered by RF-WPT. It is validated through our testbed and detailed analysis of design choices and architectural decisions are presented here. Despite challenges such as the ESL energy consumption and low harvester efficiency, this work highlights the potential for significant improvements in future iterations. The system was optimized to leverage a leaded aluminum electrolytic capacitor, balancing cost and performance, though its limited capacitance and physical size suggest that cascading buffers or transitioning to EDLCs may be necessary for higher power applications. Future work should focus on enhancing harvester sensitivity, reducing capacitor sizes, improving antenna design, and lowering operating voltages to align with component specifications. Additionally, multi-antenna WPT and initial access schemes will be investigated to further improve the overall efficiency and feasibility of next-generation ESLs. The findings and results of this work lay the groundwork for further optimizations in hardware resource efficiency and energy consumption, advancing the practicality of RF-powered ESL systems.

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